

IMPROVEMENT OF VOLTAGE PROFILE USING HYBRID INTEGRATED TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, Improvement of voltage profile by using the Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) and Cuckoo Search (CS) based hybrid integrated technique is proposed. In the proposed technique generators voltage limits and Reactive Power Flows are developed by the FLC interference rules base. Because the generators minimal reactive power component is assessed that has been utilized to distribute its real power and effectively reduce the real power loss. The CS technique helps to optimize the minimized real power loss, while the reactive power operating points of the generator. It becomes to make the proposed technique as the integrated technique, because the optimized reactive power limits effectively maintains the voltage stability and reduce the line losses. The planned incorporated technique is applied in MATLAB working platform with IEEE 30 Bus test system, the voltage profile and optimal Power flows are presented.

KEYWORDS: Voltage Profile, Line Flow, Reactive power, Optimum Reactive Power Flow (ORPF), Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) and Cuckoo Search Algorithm (CS).

INTRODUCTION

For high quality customer services, the vital operating task of power utilities is to keep voltage in a permissible range [1] [3]. Electric power loads vary from hour to hour and voltage can be varied by change of the power load [2]. In order to follow the load change, power utility operators in control centers handle a variety of equipments such as generators, transformers, static condenser, and shunt reactor, so that they can inject reactive power and control voltage directly in target power systems [4] [5]. Voltage stability constrained reactive power dispatching in deregulated power networks is a difficult task facing an Independent System Operator (ISO) that is mandated to provide equitable ancillary services [6]. Reactive power facilities are operated under a monopoly in a vertically integrated power system by the system operator to meet technical requirement [9] , such as improving the voltage profile and dropping the loss of transmission lines or, even, rising the voltage stability margin to stay away from instability, because of load perturbation or equipment failure [7], [8]. Optimal Reactive Power Flow (ORPF) is a significant tool for power system operators both in planning, operating stages and avoids instability [10] [12]. In the reactive power requirement, the change of load causes variation [11]. Within their acceptable operating limits, the amount of reactive power required for operating loads should preserve load bus voltages [22]. To meet the increased reactive power demand under heavily loaded conditions and to avoid voltage instability problems, [31].

For optimal reactive power flow such as linear programming, an extensive variety of conventional optimization techniques used [13]. To solve ORPF problem, Newton approach, interior point methods and dynamic programming have been developed [16, 23]. In general these techniques suffer due to algorithmic difficulty, insecure convergence, and sensitivity to initial search point. For setting optimal reactive power limits, the soft computing techniques fuzzy logic, fuzzy linear programming, and evolutionary programming (EP) are used [14] [15].

For secure and reliable operation in power markets H. Wu *et al.* [17] have discussed an important ancillary service. Along with a power flow tracing based method, an OPF based reactive power optimization model was proposed to undertake this problem. Ali Ozturk *et al.* [18] have studied RPO with ABC algorithm in a power system. The reactive power optimization was applied in a manner that has rare application in the literature

through this application. Not only active power loss minimization, the reactive power cost and the quality of voltage transferred to the customers were also optimized. P.R.Sujin *et al.* [19] have developed reactive OPF to resolve the optimal reactive dispatch problem. The total reactive cost was separated into generators duty and loadings duty. This method was compatible with the competitive market structure and economic effectiveness could be achieved. J. V. Parate *et al.* [20] has widespread the problem of reactive power control viewed from two aspects: load compensation and voltage support. This was utilized to decrease the total system real power loss or voltage deviation as an objective to calculate optimal settings of reactive power output or terminal voltages of generating plants, transformer tap settings and output of other compensating devices such as capacitor banks and synchronous condensers. To minimize active power loss in power systems Kursat Ayan *et al.* [21] have studied optimal reactive power flow (ORPF) based on ABC algorithm. It does not require these parameters is the advantage of ABC algorithm, since it was very hard to decide external parameters such as cross over rate and mutation rate as in case of genetic algorithm and differential evolution.

The reactive power support for a generator has two components: one for supporting its own real power transmission and the other for supplying reactive demand. For improving the system security, and controlling system voltage; and the second part should receive financial compensation in competitive power markets is the first components used. An optimum power flow (OPF) based optimization model along with a power flow tracing method, for maintaining the reactive power operating range. In this method, the optimal allocation of reactive power is based on the objective function of the system. Therefore an alternative method required for allocating reactive power losses. The ORPF is obtained by minimal assessment of the reactive power of the generating units. The adjustment of the control variables with certain limits makes the efficient operation, because the reactive power control of the generator depends on the control variables of the power system. The proposed integrated technique will be combined with fuzzy logic and cuckoo search algorithm. The fuzzy logic is one of the knowledge base intelligence techniques which will be used for determining the generator reactive power operating limits. Cuckoo search is one of the optimization algorithms which will be used for optimizing the objective function parameters. The rest of the paper organized by follows: section 3 describes the proposed work brief explanation; section 4 gives the proposed technique implementation results and the corresponding discussions; and section 5 concludes the paper.

II.PROBLEM FORMULATION

2.1 ORPF Control Variables

It The control variables of the power system are voltage magnitude of the buses; real power loss, economic dispatch, power flow equality and in equality constraints and the transformer tap settings. The control variables of the power system are given in the following equation (1).

$$CV = [PP_G, VV_G, T, QQ_{SC}] \quad (1)$$

Where, PP_G is the active power generation of buses, VV_G is the voltage magnitude of the generator, T is the transformer ratio, QQ_{SC} is the shunt compensator reactive power. The control variables are given in the following.

2.1.1. Determination of Power Loss

The control variables are the important factor for assessing minimum reactive power of the generator. In this proposed system the higher power loss bus is identified and needed to optimize using the fuzzy rules, which is used to identify the problem and compensate the ORPF problem. The fuzzy rules are generated depends on the

control variables values for the bus system. The optimization process is obtained by using the fuzzy rules. The real power loss of the bus is given in the following equation (2).

$$PP_{Loss} = \sum_{k=1}^{N_B} \sum_{l=1}^{N_B} G_{kl} [VV_k^2 - 2VV_k VV_l \cos \delta_{kl} + VV_l^2] \quad (2)$$

Where, PP_{Loss} is the active power loss, G_{kl} is the conductance of the kl^{th} transmission line, V_k and V_l are the voltage magnitude of the k and l line respectively, δ_{kl} is the angle difference of the k and l line respectively, N_B is the number of buses. The generated power consists of real and reactive power, which is given in the following section 2.1.2.

2.1.2. Determination of Power Flow Equalities

The power generated in the generator buses mainly contributes to solve the load demand of the bus and the fully utilizing the operating limits of the generators. The operating limits of every generators are restricted by their lower and the upper limits and the power flow of the transmission line contains the shunt compensating device i.e., shunt capacitor which compensate the reactive power flow of the transmission line. The real and reactive power generation of the generator bus is given in the following equation (3) and (4).

$$PP_{Gk} = PP_{LDk} + VV_k \sum_{l=1}^{N_B} VV_l (G_{kl} \cos \delta_{kl} + B_{kl} \sin \delta_{kl}) \quad (3)$$

$$QQ_{Gk} = QQ_{SCk} + QQ_{LDk} + VV_k \sum_{l=1}^{N_B} VV_l (G_{kl} \sin \delta_{kl} - B_{kl} \cos \delta_{kl}) \quad (4)$$

Where, PP_{Gk} and QQ_{Gk} are the active and reactive power generated by the generators of the k^{th} bus, PP_{LDk} and QQ_{LDk}^{\min} are the active and reactive power demand of the k^{th} bus, is the reactive load demand, G_{kl} is the conductance between k and l bus respectively, B_{kl} is the susceptance between k and l bus respectively. The active power generation, reactive power generation and the generator bus voltages are restricted by their upper and lower limits and the generator constraints are given in the following equations (5)(6) and (7).

$$PP_{Gk}^{\min} \leq PP_{Gk} \leq PP_{Gk}^{\max} \quad (5)$$

$$QQ_{Gk}^{\min} \leq QQ_{Gk} \leq QQ_{Gk}^{\max} \quad (6)$$

$$VV_k^{\min} \leq VV_k \leq VV_k^{\max} \quad (7)$$

Where, VV_k^{\min} and VV_k^{\max} is the minimum and maximum bus voltage generated, PP_{Gk}^{\min} and PP_{Gk}^{\max} is the minimum and maximum active power generated, QQ_{Gk}^{\min} and QQ_{Gk}^{\max} is the minimum

and maximum reactive power generated. The description of the control variables of the transmission line and load bus is given in the following section 2.1.3.

2.1.3. Determination of the Constraints

The transmission line consists of shunt compensating devices and the transformer tap settings, which are adjusted sequentially to minimize the reactive power generation. The shunt compensating devices are arranged in the transmission line for specified locations. It can be compensate the reactive power low of the transmission line. The shunt capacitor is act as the shunt compensating device of the proposed system; it can be generate the reactive power. The transformers tap setting also reliable for the ORPF problem. These transformer tap settings, shunt capacitor reactive power and the apparent power of the load bus are restricted by their upper and lower limits, which are given in the following equations (9) (10) and (11).

$$TT_k^{\min} \leq TT_k \leq TT_k^{\max} \quad (9)$$

$$QQ_{SCK}^{\min} \leq QQ_{SCK} \leq QQ_{SCK}^{\max} \quad (10)$$

$$SS_{LDk}^{\min} \leq SS_{LDk} \leq SS_{LDk}^{\max} \quad (11)$$

TT_k^{\min} and TT_k^{\max} is the minimum and maximum transformer tap settings limit of the k^{th} transmission line, QQ_{SCK}^{\min} and QQ_{SCK}^{\max} is the minimum and maximum of the shunt compensator reactive power generated limit for k^{th} transmission line, SS_{LDk}^{\min} and SS_{LDk}^{\max} is the minimum and maximum apparent power of the k^{th} load bus. The objective of the proposed system is minimizing the reactive power generator limits; it can be minimize the real power loss of the power system.

2.2. Formation of the Objective Function

The main objective of the proposed system is to minimize the generators reactive power generation, which subject to the equality constraints of the power flow and the inequality constraints of the voltage magnitude of the system. The equality constraints of the power flow are obtained from the generator buses and the inequality constraints voltage magnitude is obtained from the buses. The mathematical model of the proposed system can be described as the following equation (12)

$$\psi = \text{Min} \left(QQ_{SCK} + QQ_{LDk} + \sum_{l=1}^{N_k} VV_l (G_{kl} \sin \delta_{kl} - B_{kl} \cos \delta_{kl}) \right) \quad (12)$$

$$QQ_{Gk}^{\min} \leq QQ_{Gk} \leq QQ_{Gk}^{\max} \quad k \in N_G$$

$$VV_k^{\min} \leq VV_k \leq VV_k^{\max} \quad k \in N_B$$

Where, QQ_{SCK} is the reactive power generated from the shunt compensating device of the k^{th} bus, QQ_{LDk} is the reactive power demand of the k^{th} bus, VV_k^{\min} and VV_k^{\max} are the voltage magnitude of the k^{th} bus, N_G is the number of generators, N_B is the number of buses. The proposed objective function is reliable for the ORPF and the minimization of the power loss of the buses. The fuzzy logic controller is a reliable rules base controller, it is used to determine the reactive power generation of the generators. The cuckoo

search algorithm is the optimization technique to find the most correct value, which is used to find out the minimal power loss of the system.

2.3. Fuzzy Logic Controller Used to Determine the Reactive Power Generation

The Fuzzy Logic Controller is the flexible technique to adapt all the problems. In this FLC the control strategy is represented by a set of rules and it is no need to accurate set of equations to represent the system. The FLC consists of three process, i.e., fuzzification, interference engine and defuzzification. The physical values are transformed into the fuzzy values by the fuzzification process. It offers every input variable a membership function connecting to the fuzzy set. By means of a simple IF-THEN structure the fuzzy rules are prepared. They plan the inputs states into suitable output situation. Depending on the complication of the system different defuzzification techniques have been initiated [24]. The schematic diagram of the proposed FLC is given in the following figure 1.

Fig.1. Structure of the proposed FLC

In this proposed system, the real power is the physical input of the fuzzy logic and the rules are generated depending on the real power input. The fuzzy rules has been generated by the three categories i.e., low, medium and high. The expert knowledge proposed fuzzy rules base is following, if real power is low then the reactive power is low, if the real power is medium then the reactive power is low and if the real power is high then the reactive power is medium. These rules are used to assign the generator reactive power generation. In this generation limit is given to the optimization algorithm, it can be lead the minimized power loss of the system. The power loss can be determined by the following section 2.4.

2.4. Determination of Minimized Power Loss Using the Cuckoo Search

Based on manner life of Cuckoo bird, one of the newly grown bioinspired algorithms is the Cuckoo Search (CS). Cuckoos utilize a forceful strategy of reproduction that occupies the female hew nests of other birds to put down their eggs fertilized. Occasionally, the egg of cuckoo in the nest is revealed and the hacked birds throw away or abandon the nest and begin their own offspring somewhere else. Based on the subsequent three idealized rules, the Cuckoo Search was proposed by Yang and Deb 2009 [26] and they are:

- Every cuckoo lays one egg at a time, and deposits it in a erratically chosen nest;
- The top nests with high class of eggs (solutions) will take over to the next generations;
- The number of existing host nests is fixed, and a host can find out an alien egg with a possibility $pa \in [0,1]$. In this case, to build an entirely new nest in a new place the host bird can either throw the egg away or discard the nest so as.

An essential advantage of this algorithm is its plainness. There is basically only a single parameter in CS (apart from the population size) comparing with other population- or agent-based metaheuristic algorithms such as particle swarm optimization and harmony search [25].

Once the process is finished the network is ready to give the minimized power loss and corresponding generator reactive power limits. The proposed method is analyzed with the IEEE 14 bus system and it has been implemented into the MATLAB platform.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The IEEE 30 bus system is generator reactive power limits, voltage stability, power loss and fuel costs are analyzed in the MATLAB platform. The IEEE 30 bus system has six generator bus, 21 load bus and 41 transmission lines. The FLC consists of three process, i.e., fuzzification, interference and defuzzification. The generator reactive power limit is determined by the FLC. The FLC can be producing the reactive power generation limits depending on the expert knowledge rules base. The optimal reactive power limit has been identified using the cuckoo search algorithm. It is optimization algorithm, which determines the minimized power loss of the bus system and corresponding reactive power limits of the generators. The proposed system also analyzes the voltage stability and the fuel cost of the system, which is given in the following. The proposed IEEE 30 system structure is given in the following figure 2.

Fig.2. Proposed tested IEEE 30 bus system structure

The Figure 2 shows the proposed IEEE 30 bus tested system structure, which consists of six generator bus, 21 load bus and 41 transmission lines. Table 1 illustrates the best real and reactive power generation limits of the six generator bus, i.e., 1, 2, 5, 8, 11 and 13 respectively, and the best minimal power loss of the IEEE 30 bus system. The voltage stability of the six generator bus is 1.0600, 1.0430, 1.0277, 1.0134, 1.0459 and 1.0710 (all values are in pu) respectively. The Normal loss of the proposed IEEE 30 bus system is 12.4964 MW and it could be reduced at 5.23MW. It also has the generator real power minimum and maximum operating limits. The table

2 shows IEEE 30 bus system line losses, i.e., the 41 transmission line real and reactive line losses. Figure 3 illustrates the proposed system voltage stability at every bus, which would be represents IEEE 30 bus system voltage variation. In this proposed IEEE 30 bus system 1 to 30 buses are maintained at various voltage levels, which is on stable condition. The standard voltage stability limit of the power system is lies between 0.95 to

1.05 pu. The voltage profile is maintained at the limit is $V_{min} = 0.976$ to $V_{max} = 1.051$ pu. The power loss is varies with the increasing number of iterations. At the first iteration the power loss is 12.4964 MW, which is assign to the normal power loss of the system. The iteration range has been increased into the 100 of the proposed technique; the power loss could be reduced at 5.23MW in the 100th iteration. The above discussion shows proposed system perfectly maintains the voltage profile of the bus and the power loss

TABLE.1.

Best real and reactive power limit with minimum power loss

Generator bus	Normal loss	Generators real and reactive power generation limits in (MW)				Best DG real and reactive power limits		Voltage	Minimum power loss using the cuckoo search method
	MW	P_{min}	P_{max}	Q_{min}	Q_{max}	P_{best}	Q_{best}	Pu	MW
1	12.4964	50	200	-20	0	151.701	-10.1684	1.0600	5.23
2		20	80	-20	20	72.910	-19.4793	1.0430	
5		15	50	-15	15	36.437	2.0044	1.0277	
8		10	35	-15	15	25.185	-11.233	1.0134	
11		10	30	-10	10	23.247	0.0746	1.0459	
13		12	40	-15	15	15.301	-2.6423	1.0710	

Fig.3. Voltage variation of the proposed system

TABLE.2.

IEEE 30 bus system line loss using the proposed method

Line no	Bus number		Line loss in (MW)		Line no	Bus number		Line loss in (MW)	
	From bus	To bus	Real power	Reactive power		From bus	To bus	Real power	Reactive power
1	1	2	0.548	1.642	22	15	18	0.081	0.166
2	1	3	0.512	1.871	23	18	19	0.019	0.039
3	2	4	0.254	0.774	24	19	20	0.008	0.016
4	3	4	0.135	0.389	25	10	20	0.048	0.108
5	2	5	0.718	3.016	26	10	17	0.001	0.003
6	2	6	0.428	1.299	27	10	21	0.115	0.248
7	4	6	0.094	0.328	28	10	22	0.079	0.163
8	5	7	0.154	0.389	29	21	23	0.001	0.002
9	6	7	0.224	0.687	30	15	23	0.124	0.250
10	6	8	0.009	0.032	31	22	24	0.046	0.071
11	6	9	0.000	0.109	32	23	24	0.029	0.060
12	6	10	0.000	0.289	33	24	25	0.032	0.056
13	9	11	-0.000	1.604	34	25	26	0.047	0.070
14	9	10	0.000	1.190	35	25	27	0.051	0.098
15	4	12	0.000	0.859	36	28	27	-0.000	0.942
16	12	13	0.000	2.339	37	27	29	0.089	0.168
17	12	14	0.111	0.230	38	27	30	0.167	0.314
18	12	15	0.394	0.776	39	29	30	0.035	0.065
19	12	16	0.158	0.331	40	8	28	0.008	0.026
20	14	15	0.025	0.023	41	6	28	0.026	0.092
21	16	17	0.069	0.161	-	-	-	-	-

IV.CONCLUSION

Fuzzy Logic and Cuckoo Search Based Integrated Technique for Modeling Optimal Reactive Power Flow (ORPF) has been proposed by us in this thesis. The planned method has been applied in the MATLAB platform. The ORPF problem was conquered by the planned method. In the planned incorporated method is united with fuzzy logic and cuckoo search algorithm. One of the knowledge base intelligence techniques was the fuzzy logic which has been utilized for verifying the generator reactive power operating limits. One of the optimization algorithms was Cuckoo search which has been used for optimizing the intention function parameters. The planned examined IEEE 30 bus system best true and reactive power generation limits, voltage stability and power loss is evaluated. The planned system voltage stability has been uphold at *0.976 to 1.06 pu*, and the power loss would be reduced at *5.23 MW*. The examined results confirmed that the planned technique consist of the improved presentation which is practiced over other techniques.

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